

Accretion behaviour during binary star formation

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Binaries of separations $\lesssim 10$ AU cannot form in situ during molecular core collapse because the initial hydrostatic core that collapses to form the protostar has a radius of ~ 5 AU [1], and this hydrostatic core is not susceptible to fragmentation during the second protostellar collapse phase [2]. Therefore, binaries with a semi-major axis $a \lesssim 10$ AU likely form via the in-spiral of an initially wider binary, possibly via viscous evolution through discs [3]. During viscous evolution of the gas disc, the angular momentum of the binary can be transferred to the gas, thus shrinking the orbit of the binary. During this dynamical evolution, accretion events may be triggered.

In this proceedings, I summarise the work published in [4], where we investigated any dependence of eccentricity and the accretion rate during accretion bursts triggered by a binary companion.

Methods

We use the adaptive mesh refinement (AMR) code FLASH [5] to integrate the compressible ideal MHD equations. The size of the three-dimensional computational domain is ~ 8000 AU³ and with AMR, we obtain a resolution of ~ 1.95 AU when fully refined. At this resolution the accretion radius of the sink particles is $r_{\text{sink}} \sim 4.9$ AU.

Our simulations begin with a spherical cloud of mass $1 M_{\odot}$, and radius ~ 3300 AU placed in the centre of the simulation domain. The cloud is initially given solid body rotation with angular momentum of 1.85×10^{51} g cm² s⁻¹. An initially uniform magnetic field of $100 \mu\text{G}$ is also threaded through the cloud in the z -direction. The cloud is initially given a uniform density of $\rho_0 = 3.82 \times 10^{-18}$ g cm⁻³, and a density perturbation is imposed on the cloud. This is to seed the formation of a binary-star system. An initial turbulent velocity field is imposed on top of the solid body rotation. We run two simulations with turbulence of Mach number $\mathcal{M} = 0.1$ and 0.2 , which are referred to as $T1$ and $T2$ hereafter.

Analysis and Results

The binary star systems form in the simulations and evolve. They accrete mass and during the early in-spiral of the binaries, we observed spikes in accretion correlated with the periastron passage of the binaries. In order to understand the dependence of accretion bursts and eccentricity, the accretion data of the binaries needs to be phase-folded. To do this, the times of periastron and apastron must be found and are defined as orbital phase, $\phi = 0$ and 0.5 , respectively. After these are found, the sink particle data is divided into ten time bins between each periastron and apastron, which results in a total of 20 time bins or phase-space bins between consecutive periastrons. In each bin, the average accretion rate $\langle \dot{M} \rangle$ is calculated. After the phase-folding is completed, the median accretion rate in each phase-space bin is calculated and the orbit-to-orbit variation for each bin is taken to be the 16th and 84th percentile. Since the eccentricity of the binary is also evolving over the course of the

simulations, it is not appropriate to phase-fold the accretion over the entire duration of the simulation. In order to study the dependence of the intensity of episodic accretion on eccentricity, we define eccentricity bins to phase-fold over. For $T1$, these eccentricity bins were selected to be $e = [1.1, 0.7, 0.5, 0.4, 0.3, 0.2, 0.1, 0.0]$. As the eccentricity in $T2$ reduces at a faster rate than in $T1$, these same bins were not appropriate for $T2$, because in some bins only two orbits would be folded. Thus, for $T2$, we adjusted the bins to be $e = [1.1, 0.7, 0.5, 0.3, 0.1, 0.0]$.

To determine the strength of a burst, we calculate β , which is the ratio between the burst (\dot{M}_b) and quiescent (\dot{M}_q) accretion rates. \dot{M}_b is the average accretion rate between phases $0.8 < \phi < 1.1$. \dot{M}_q is taken to be the average accretion rate between phases $0.2 < \phi < 0.75$. β against eccentricity is shown in Figure 1, and we find $\beta \sim 1$ for eccentricities $e < 0.2$, i.e. consistent with no episodic accretion. For $T1$, the strength of episodic accretion peaks at moderate eccentricities, $0.2 < e < 0.6$. A similar trend is seen for $T2$ with higher eccentricities displaying stronger episodic accretion up to the highest eccentricities. While $T1$ peaks at $\beta \sim 3$, $T2$ produces higher β for higher eccentricity. This may suggest some dependence of the strength of episodic accretion on the level of turbulence, with stronger turbulence producing stronger accretion. Based on the derived β values, we approximate that binaries with eccentricities $e \gtrsim 0.2$ should display episodic accretion.

Figure 1: Strength of accretion vs binary eccentricity.

To understand the mechanism which drives the accretion rate, we look closely at the periastron passage of one of our high-resolution simulations. Projections of this is shown in Figure 2. We see from the figure that the approach of the companion distorts the circumstellar disc, which excites a spiral wave. It is the approach of the companion that removes angular momentum from the gas in the outer disc due to the different angular velocities. This angular momentum is transferred from the

Figure 2: Zoom in projections of the first periastron in our high-resolution simulation. The solid lines are density contours spaced evenly in log-space.

gas to the stellar orbits. After periastron, we see that the material is ejected outward, and this is because momentum from the binary orbit is imparted into the gas to push it to higher orbits, and the binary separation is reduced. From looking at the evolution of the orbital angular momentum, we observe the accretion event begins before periastron when the spiral wave is excited. We also observe the orbital angular momentum of the binary components increases due to the exchange between the binary and circumstellar discs before periastron. The orbital angular momentum then decreases after periastron, because of the ejection of gas. From this close analysis of an accretion burst, we find that an accretion event is ultimately triggered by angular momentum moving from the circumstellar discs to the binary orbit, exciting the spiral wave.

Conclusions

We quantified how eccentricity influences the strength of accretion over a binary orbit, what physical mechanism triggers accretion events.

Dependence of episodic accretion on eccentricity: We find that orbital phase-correlated episodic accretion occurs in binaries of eccentricity $e > 0.2$. For *T1*, we find that episodic accretion peaks for moderate eccentricity ($0.3 < e < 0.7$). *T2* shows a general linear trend of weak episodic accretion at low eccentricity to strong accretion at high eccentricity. These varying results imply

that eccentricity alone does not determine the strength of episodic accretion.

Mechanism triggering accretion events: Based on high-resolution simulations, we determine that it is primarily torques between the circumstellar disc and the companion that triggers an accretion event. Observations of spiral arms in protoplanetary discs show similar structures to those seen in our simulations [6].

Overall we find that episodic accretion can be seen in binaries with eccentricity > 0.2 , and the shape of episodic accretion is in good agreement with that found in observations of short-period binaries (this is investigated in [4]). We suggest that signs of episodic accretion should be observable in long-period binaries.

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References

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